

APPENDIX A - Use of the PyMOL program.

Load the image using the "*fetch 3vik*" command. Then, change the preview to "cartoon".

Select the ligand (cbi) and display it as sticks. Then, change the color scheme.

Finally, save in VRML 2 (.wrl Extension) format.

APPENDIX B - Use of Blender software.

Import the ".wrl" file using Blender's import option.

Export to FBX format.

APPENDIX C - Use of EnTiTi Creator programs.

Open EnTiTi Creator, log in (create an account if you do not have one), create a new project by clicking "Empty project", and type a name for the project below.

After loading the main area, click Library and then upload to submit the template.

Upload the FBX file and then return to the "Scene" tab. Double-click "Target image" to select the reference image.

Upload an image, click it, and then the right-pointing arrow. Finally, click on "Preview selected in scene". On the main screen, now click "3D Model" and drag to the checkered region. Double-click on the square and select the loaded model.

Reduce the model's size in the "Scale" tab of the "Object info" panel. Then insert the light into the environment by dragging the "3D Light" button to the checkered area.

Click on the "Save" button to save and then go to "Publish" to make your project publicly available.

APPENDIX D - Use of ENTiTi Viewer programs.

On a smartphone (Android or IOS), download the ENTiTi Viewer app. The device must have a gyroscope, accelerometer, and camera.

Open the app and search for the project name. For example, in the figure below, we looked for "beta-glicosidase", but the project created previously is called "3vik". Click on the play button to see the augmented reality.

Print the reference image, then position the camera as indicated by the application. The augmented reality model will appear on paper.

Move the camera and observe the protein model.

